

THE INSIGHT OF A GREEK STORY OF EPIMETHUS AND PANDORA AND EXPLAINING OF ITS VALUE AND ITS HELP IN UNDERSTANDING OF OUR LIFE EXPERIENCES

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ABSTRACT

The article is about transforming our experiences and worldviews through the Greek myth “Epimethus and Pandora”. It describes how to reform our thoughts by understanding the insights of the myth. It puts light on how to reflect back to our life experiences by the point of having hope and gives example on applying it.

Key words: archtypical story, myth, a flash of insight, hope, transforming.

Intro

From our childhood, we are taught stories or later life myths that are moral and prompts us which way is the most righteous way to choose in our life paths. The myth of Pandora very reminded me of the story of Adam and Eva where a woman couldn't hold her lust from eating the forbidden fruit and ate anyway and expelled from Paradise. After they came to Earth, they are told to live in here doing good deeds only and praying only Allah and following his words disregarding to Shaytan(evil)'s jinx and tricks. Just like in the Pandora, there are good and bad angels in the Qur'an, of Muslim religious book, who lead people into the doing meritorious or sinful work. It is guaranteed to get into Paradise if we comply of Allah's commands or into the hell if we follow with Evil's words. Thus, we are given choice, and it is up to each human being to choose how to live his given lifetime.

Main part.

T Also, there are hundreds of stories in the Qur'an, which describes lots of incidents when people not listened to their creator and continued in their wrongful work, and have seen it's outcomes in their current life or the worst ones are left to be given in their afterward life. It is amazing to note how the word "punishment" in the Qur'an came 117 times, while the word "forgiveness" repeated 234 times which is roughly double time more than the prior. Qur'an teaches us not only how to live a faithful life, but also, not to get vanished when met with the hardships of it. I see the likeness of the myth of Pandora and the events in the Qur'an, in their giving hope to their reader.

As I became acknowledged, these stories are called Archtypical stories, and they have a particular serve in guiding people *and helping to see the larger meaning of our experience, that instigates an "Aha," a flash of insight*, writes Janice E.Clark in *Of Writing, Imagination and Dialogue* article.

As I was recently found myself got into down of the hopelessness and experienced a deep sorrow for myself during that time, I remembered how it was hurtful of losing hope and because of which all other ills also came to hug me.

While studying one of my University's courses I became ill suddenly and could not do my lessons for nearly month. Being left from the assignments, I tried to find other ways of completing the course like taking 1-month probation or having to retake the course. Unfortunately, it came out, I used my limits already and I have only two weeks to complete which I thought I can do it if I take a two-day holiday (the most days that can be given from my work) and within weekends I can finish assignments. Nevertheless, when I started them to do, the excesses of undone tasks scared me, and I thought it is impossible to finish them and gave up myself even before trying it. So, I spent my first off-day with staring at my laptop and crying finding myself in a block way and thinking about all the negatives around my life; why nobody of my close people did not help, why I believed I would be given a chance, but not given, and all-other bad thoughts chased me into the corner of the depression and hopelessness.

Being under pressure, I started to search little joy for myself, that release me from the bad aura I was having, I stood up and go out to walk for one-hour. I enjoyed the nature and within good picture, some positive thoughts started to sparkle in my mind. I remembered how supportive my family is, and they will still love me no matter I fail the course or not. They are ready to give me any help I need without questioning me, so I thought why not to try until the end of the week as much as I can, no matter what result will be at the end. And when I started to do them with a feeling of love and care for myself, things started to work. My friends handed me their help, my family greatly stood by me, and amazingly, Professor did not let me down but helped with the most of the deadlines and markings.

Conclusion

At the moment I lost the hope for finishing the course, I closed all the doors in front of me and turned to darkness. However, the spiritual and the moral knowledge inside of me helped me to make the right choice at last and be on a positive side. This knowledge is definitely gained when we watered our minds with the fiction stories and legends that was inherited by our ancestors and what are experienced by them and sent to us.

Reference

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